

Organomercury(II)-dithiocarbamate complexes : synthesis, characterization and fungicidal activity

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A number of organomercury(II)-dithiocarbamate complexes of the types, $p\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{HgL}^1$ (I) and $p\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{HgL}^2$ (II), where X = Me, MeO, NO₂; L¹ = phenyldithiocarbamate; L² = *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate, have been synthesised. Conductance data indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes. From ir and uv studies, the bonding modes of the ligands to the organomercury(II) moieties have been elucidated. The ¹³C nmr spectra support the stoichiometry of the complexes. The fragmentation pattern has been analysed on the basis of mass spectra. The compounds have been tested for fungicidal activity.

Dithiocarbamates constitute an important class of fungicidal compounds¹. The mode of fungicidal action of the dithiocarbamates involves the inhibition of hexose monophosphate oxidation pathway of carbohydrate metabolism². Both glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase and 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase show high sensitivity to various dithiocarbamates. The inhibition of these enzymes can be obtained with dithiocarbamates at concentrations as low as 10⁻⁵M. The inhibitory properties of these compounds have been attributed to their ability to interfere with sulphhydryl groups necessary for enzymatic activity³. The organomercurials constitute another class of fungicidal compounds, which act by combining with cellular proteins and enzymes containing sulphhydryl functions⁴.

In the present study, model complexes containing both the dithiocarbamate and organomercury(II) groups have been synthesised. The two chemical groups are expected to supplement each other for their fungicidal activity. This in continuation to our investigation of organomercury(II)-biomolecule interaction⁵.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The complexes are brown in colour and soluble in DMF, DMSO and THF. Conductance data indicate that these compounds are non-electrolytes.

Ir spectra : Whether the dithiocarbamate group is monodentate or bidentate is reflected in the $\nu_{\text{C}\cdots\text{S}}$ frequency. The presence of only one strong band at ~1000 cm⁻¹ supports the bidentate behaviour, a doublet being expected in

case of monodentate behaviour⁶. In the present complexes, only one medium intensity band was observed at ~1000 cm⁻¹, which supports the bidentate nature of the dithiocarbamate moiety.

The band at ~1375 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C}\cdots\text{N}}$ frequency. The occurrence of this band at lower energy as compared to the corresponding dialkyldithiocarbamate com-

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analytical data

Compd.	Dec. temp. °C	Yield %	Hg% : Found/(Calcd.)
<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ HgL ¹	109	55	43.57 (43.63)
<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ HgL ¹	126	32	42.10 (42.15)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ HgL ¹	115	88	40.93 (40.87)
<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ HgL ²	185	46	39.78 (39.74)
<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ HgL ²	245	36	38.58 (38.52)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ HgL ²	237	45	37.49 (37.44)

*All compounds gave satisfactory S and N analyses.

plexes indicates considerably less double bond character of $C\equiv N^7$. The ν_{Hg-S} mode absorbed⁸ at $\sim 375\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Uv spectra: The uv spectra of the complexes showed a band at $\sim 288\text{ nm}$ ($\log \epsilon \sim 4.5$) due to intraligand $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the $N\equiv C\equiv S$ group⁹. The ligands sodium phenyldithiocarbamate and sodium *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate displayed a band at 304 ($\log \epsilon 3.7$) and 340 nm ($\log \epsilon 3.5$), respectively. This band is assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the $S\equiv C\equiv S$ chromophore and is associated to the inequivalence of $C\equiv S$ bonds¹⁰. The absence of this band in the complexes shows that the dithiocarbamate moieties act as S-S bidentate bonding groups.

¹³C nmr spectra: The ¹³C nmr spectra of sodium dithiocarbamates showed a resonance signal at $\sim 171\text{ ppm}$ due to the CS_2 group¹¹. In the complexes, this signal appeared at $\sim 174\text{ ppm}$. The downfield shift was attributed to the involvement of sulphur atoms in complexation.

Mass spectra: The mass spectral analysis of phenyldithiocarbamate and *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate complexes are shown in Scheme 1. Initially, the fragment 1 ($R = H$, $m/z 369$; $R = NO_2$, 414) was formed. It cleaved through two pathways. Pathway (i) involved the loss of HgS , resulting in ion 2 ($R = H$, $m/z 136$; $R = NO_2$, 181). Pathway (ii) resulted in the formation of ion 3 ($R = H$, $m/z 293$; $R = NO_2$, 338) and fragment 4 ($m/z 76$)¹².

Scheme 1. Fragmentation pattern of (a) phenyldithiocarbamate complexes and (b) *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate.

Fungicidal activity: The complexes were screened for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *A. fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*¹³ at 25 and $50\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. The complexes had greater antifungal activity than the corresponding sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids. The complexes showed a higher fungicidal activity (39–74% inhibition) at higher concentration ($50\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) than that (36–71%) at lower concentration ($25\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The antifungal activity of these compounds is comparable to that of standard mercurial fungicides, such as thiomersal, phenylmercury acetate and ethylmercury chloride⁴. The or-

der of activity with respect to the fungus species was *A. niger* > *C. albicans* > *A. fumigatus*.

For each series of complexes, the biological activity varied with the nature of substituent (X) on the phenylmercury(II) group. The order of activity with respect to the complexes was $X = NO_2 > Me > MeO$. This may be explained on the basis of the kinetic lability of the complexes. The electron-withdrawing nitro group is expected to weaken the metal-ligand bond. This made the *p*-nitro derivatives kinetically labile. Since the methyl and methoxy groups have electron-releasing characteristics, these substituents strengthened the metal-ligand bond. The lability of the complexes was lowered and so was their antifungal activity. The methoxy group has a greater electron-releasing tendency than the methyl group. Hence the activities of the methoxy analogs are lower than those of the corresponding methyl substituted derivatives.

Experimental

The following instruments were used: Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge; Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer; Perkin-Elmer 554 UV-VIS spectrophotometer; FX-200 FT-NMR spectrometer for ¹³C nmr spectra; Jeol JMS DX-303 spectrometer for mass spectra.

Sodium phenyldithiocarbamate and sodium *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate¹⁴ and arylmercury(II) chlorides, *p*- XC_6H_4HgCl ($X = Me, MeO, NO_2$)¹⁵ were prepared by reported methods. Mercury was estimated gravimetrically as mercury(II) sulphide¹⁶.

A solution (25 ml) of *p*- XC_6H_4HgCl (0.01 mol) in DMF was slowly added to a solution (25 ml) of sodium phenyldithiocarbamate (0.01 mol) in DMF. The contents were stirred for 4 h at 50° and filtered. The filtrate was slowly added to crushed ice with vigorous stirring. The precipitate so obtained was washed successively with hot water and benzene. The resulting product was crystallised from THF. The *p*-nitrophenyldithiocarbamate complexes were prepared by following a similar sequence of operations.

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